

Eighteen Years Young

Journey Through the Universe celebrates 18 years of community engagement — with a bright future ahead under NOIRLab

Peter Michaud (NSF's NOIRLab)

If you haven't heard of NOIRLab's flagship annual outreach program *Journey Through the Universe* (*Journey*), it's not for lack of persistence! Just completing 18 consecutive years of local community engagement in Hawai'i, *Journey* continues to grow and develop in new and exciting ways.

One of the most significant changes to *Journey* has happened in the past two years, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. For most of its long history, *Journey*, managed by Gemini North staff (and led by Janice Harvey, see sidebar on page 37), focused mostly on in-classroom, in-person programming. In a typical year *Journey* programming reaches 300+ classrooms and over 8000 individual students. However, because of COVID, for the past two years *Journey* pivoted to virtual programming, which has proven to be a challenge in many ways, but also presented a number of unexpected opportunities.

First, a little background for those who are not familiar with the program. The *Journey* program in Hawai'i began in 2004 as part of a national initiative started in 1999, led by Jeff Goldstein at NASA's National Center for Earth and Space Science Education (NCESSE) and managed by USRA (the NCESSE *Journey Through the Universe* webpages can be found [here](#)). Over the years, about 20 communities around the US participated in the program, with Gemini joining in 2005. Then, in 2006, the NASA funding came to a close and the program began operating in cost recovery mode. Since then

most of the original participating communities have been unable to sustain the program (according to the website, only Hawai'i and Washington DC continue running the program). As the national program shrank, the Hawai'i program was just hitting its stride!

The release of the Decadal Survey report (*Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics*) in November of 2021 included a focus on Community Based Science. This concept is not new; in fact the *Journey* program incorporated this principle since its inception, with immersion of STEM professionals and resources in local host communities. A major factor contributing to the success of the Hawai'i *Journey* program is a strong partnership with the local Department of Education (DOE). It cannot be overstated that a program like *Journey* needs the full support of local educators to succeed. For the past 18 years the Gemini-DOE partnership has been a model of effective community engagement and synergy.

So how does *Journey* exemplify the Community Based Science model highlighted in the Decadal Survey report?

At its very core *Journey* immerses observatory staff in the community (Figures 1 & 2). Each year during "Journey week," which generally happens in late February/early March, up to 60 staff from Gemini/NOIRLab, most of the Maunakea Observatories, NASA, and beyond, converge on Hawai'i Island schools. These astronomy educators each prepare a

presentation and are encouraged to include a hands-on activity to lead with students. To this end, an annual workshop for astronomy educators is held which shares best practices, how to align with the Next Generation Science Standards that teachers are required to adhere to, and ideas and activities that work effectively for elementary through high school students. At the end of a typical *Journey* week over 300 local classrooms are engaged in the science of astronomy and STEM disciplines.

In addition to classroom visits, *Journey* week includes multiple career panels where STEM professionals share their career experiences with students and describe what inspired them to devote

their careers to astronomy (or other STEM careers such as engineering or support roles at observatories). These career panels have become an integral part of the *Journey* activities and provide fascinating and inspiring perspectives on careers in STEM that students can relate to and identify role models for their own aspirations.

Another core principle of *Journey* and Community Based Science is community partnerships. In addition to the DOE, over 50 community businesses, institutions and organizations are active partners in the *Journey* program. These partners include everything from local car dealerships, the local daily newspaper,

Figure 1. The author gets help from students using carbon dioxide snow to wash dust off a mirror much like is done with the Gemini telescope mirrors. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

Figure 2: Gemini Director Jennifer Lotz participates in a *Journey Through the Universe* classroom presentation. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

Education & Engagement

Journey Through the Universe Hawai'i Island

Astronomy Educators in the Community 2022 (*virtually)

	Alexis Ann Acochido	EAO/JCMT
	Andy Adamson	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Tishanna Ben	National Solar Observatory/DKIST
	Vanashree Bhalotia	UH-Manoa Physics & Astronomy
	Ravinder Bhatia	Thirty Meter Telescope
	Christopher Browne	AURA / KPNO
	Lars L. Christensen	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Devin Chu	UCLA
	Brian Day	NASA SERVI
	Xinnan Du	KIPAC/Stanford
	Angelic Ebberts	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Jocelyn Ferrara	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Scott Fisher	University of Oregon
	Mimi Fuchs	Graduate student at Drexel University
	Abhinat Gautam	UCLA
	Tom Geballe	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Kristina Gibbs	NASA SERVI
	Jeff Goldstein	NCESSE
	Olivier Gizon	Subaru Telescope
	John Hamilton	UH-Hilo Physics & Astronomy
	Janice Harvey	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Saeko S. Hayashi	TMT Japan Project & Subaru Telescope
	Stephanie Henry	NASA Marshall Space Flight Center
	Ardis Herrold	Rubin Observatory
	Matthew Hosek	UCLA
	Solveig Irvine	NASA / PMPO
	Paul Jeffers	NSO
	Russell Kackley	Subaru Telescope
	Carolyn Kaichi	UH Institute for Astronomy
	Yoko Kakazu	TMT Japan Project & Subaru Telescope
	Markus Kissler-Patig	European Southern Observatory
	Kelly Kosmo O'Neil	UCLA
	Preethi Krishnamoorthy	Subaru Telescope
	Mary Beth Laychak	Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope
	Fengshun Lu	TMT
	Alexandra Lockwood	Space Telescope Science Institute
	Jennifer Lutz	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Julien Lutz	Subaru Telescope
	Leinani Lutz	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Nadine Manset	Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope
	Jomeka Marshall	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Callie Motulonis	EAO/JCMT
	Anseerh McBride	AURA (Corporate Office)
	Peter Michaud	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Joseph Mimafra	NASA SERVI
	Brian Mitchell	NASA Marshall Space Flight Center
	Junichi Noumaru	Subaru Telescope
	Brialyñ Onodera	AURA / NSO / DKIST
	Emily Peavy	Imiloa Astronomy Center
	Shelly Pelfrey	W.M. Keck Observatory
	Joy Pollard	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Claire Rafferty	National Solar Observatory
	Laurie Rousseau-Nepton	Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope
	Julien Rousselet	Subaru Telescope
	Therese Sampia	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Tom Schad	National Solar Observatory/DKIST
	Justine Schain	NSF's NOIRLab
	Doug Simons	Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope
	Robert Sparks	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Chance Spencer	CSU Fresno
	Marianne Takamiya	UH-Hilo Physics & Astronomy
	Ichi Tanaka	Subaru Telescope
	Alex Tetarenko	Texas Tech University
	Niki Thomas	UCSC
	Tomo Usuda	NAOJ TMT Project
	Fuchs Usuda-Sato	Subaru Telescope NAOJ
	Sebastien Vievard	Subaru telescope
	Andrea Waiters	SMA
	Connie Walker	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Cam Wipper	CFHT
	Syt Xu	Gemini Observatory/NSF's NOIRLab
	Michitoshi Yoshida	Subaru Telescope

For more information contact Janice Harvey at: janice.harvey@noirlab.edu noirlab.edu/public/education/journey-through-the-universe/

Figure 4: Journey Through the Universe community ambassador training event. This annual training prepares ambassadors who work with classroom presenters with logistics, introductions, and general assistance. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

supermarkets and educational institutions such as the ‘Imiloa Astronomy Education Center, University of Hawai‘i, NASA and more (Figure 3). Partnerships like these provide a way for the community to engage in the program in a tangible way and support education in the community. Each year the two local Hawai‘i Island Chambers of Commerce host a Thank You Reception for all of the *Journey* business partners, teachers, and observatory staff who share their time with students in classroom presentations and career panels.

Also included in *Journey* activities are teacher workshops, public lectures, family science days and more (although these don’t all happen during *Journey* week, and COVID has required suspending some of these events temporarily).

For the past two years (during the pandemic) all *Journey* programming has been 100% virtual, with Zoom classroom presentations/activities, virtual Thank You Receptions and career panels. In some cases *Journey* will continue with virtual elements even after the pandemic. One area where virtual presentations make sense is for some

career panels and when presenters cannot travel to Hawai‘i but want to participate and share. In these cases we will continue to keep the virtual option as an alternative for presenters.

A new element of *Journey* for 2022 (which happened in late February/early March) was a virtual education/culture exchange between Hawai‘i, Arizona and Chile (all three NOIRLab site host communities). Called *Journey Through NOIRLab*, this program enabled students and teachers to share cultural and educational experiences with classes at the other NOIRLab sites in an environment that encouraged sharing questions, dreams, and cultures. NOIRLab plans to continue to expand this event in future years and engage more students from across NOIRLab as participants.

Despite changes ahead, NOIRLab staff are excited to continue and grow the *Journey* program across all NOIRLab sites. We encourage all staff and stakeholders of NOIRLab to consider participating in the *Journey* program; to learn more about participating in future *Journey* programs please contact: peter.michaud@noirlab.edu

Those who are familiar with the *Journey Through the Universe* program in Hawai‘i will know that Janice Harvey is the inexhaustible energy source that keeps the *Journey* engine humming. Janice has managed the program since it began over 18 years ago and has kept a laser-like focus on making sure the program continues to meet the needs of teachers, students, and the community at large.

Janice’s commitment and passion for the program are obvious to anyone who knows her, and her concern for students and their futures is at the core of her lifelong commitment to bettering the community. As Janice says, “*It’s all about the keiki!*” (keiki being Hawaiian for children).

This year, after 22+ years at Gemini, and more recently NOIRLab, Janice is planning to retire. It is difficult to imagine the program without her and there is no question that it will be a different program without her at the helm. However, NOIRLab is committed to keeping *Journey* alive and vibrant and building on the remarkable legacy that Janice leaves behind. Her exceptional work to make the *Journey* program what it is today sets a very high bar that we will all strive for as the *Journey* continues!

Figure 3. (left) *Journey Through the Universe* local partner and classroom educators poster for 2022. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

This ethereal image, captured from Chile by the International Gemini Observatory looks as delicate as a butterfly's wing. It is, however, a structure known as the Chamaeleon Infrared Nebula, which is located near the center of the even larger Chamaeleon I dark cloud, one of the nearest star-forming regions in our Milky Way. *Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*